

Two astronomical phenomena that cannot be explained by the heliocentric theory

NuoFu Chen¹

¹School of New Energy, North China Electric Power University, Beijing 102206, China,
Email: nfchen@ncepu.edu.cn

Abstract

The heliocentric model well explains the sunrise, sunset and the changes of four seasons. However, this model cannot explain why the direction of a constellation changes with the seasons, and why the same stars can be observed all year round. In order to explain the two astronomical phenomena the heliocentric model is improved. The earth is fixed on the side of the sun. Except the moon, which revolves around the earth, all the other planets revolve around the sun. The rotation of the earth around its axis produces sunrise and sunset. At the same time, the earth's axis rotates around the axis perpendicular to the ecliptic plane to produce the four seasons of spring, summer, autumn and winter. Therefore, some stars, including the Big Dipper, can be observed in all seasons on the earth, but their directions and orientations are different.

Key Words: Earth < Planetary Systems, stars: activity < Stars, (stars:) binaries: general < Stars

1. Introduction

As long ago as 340 B.C. the Greek philosopher Aristotle thought that the earth was stationary and that the sun, the moon, the planets, and the stars moved in circular orbits around the earth. This idea was elaborated by Ptolemy in the second century A.D. into a complete cosmological model. After more than a thousand year, a different model was proposed in 1514 by a Polish, Nicholas Copernicus. His idea was that the sun was stationary at the center, and that the earth and the planets moved in circular orbits around the sun. Nearly a century passed before Copernicus' idea was taken seriously. Until 1609, the Italian, Galileo Galilei found that, with a telescope, the planet Jupiter was accompanied by several small satellites that orbited around it. This implied that everything did not have to orbit directly around the earth, as Aristotle and Ptolemy had thought. An explanation was provided much later, in 1687, when Sir Isaac Newton published his *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica* (Newton, 2008). Newton postulated a law of universal gravitation according to which each body in the universe was attracted toward every other by a force that was stronger the more massive the bodies and the closer they were to each other. Newton went on to show that, according to his law, gravity causes the moon to move in an elliptical orbit around the earth, and causes the earth and the planets to follow elliptical paths around the sun. By then, the heliocentric model had been perfected. Although Einstein's general theory of relativity predicted a slightly different motion from Newton's theory, it has been universally accepted that the earth travels around the sun in an elliptical orbit for more than four centuries.

According to the heliocentric model, when the earth revolves around the sun, the direction of its axis remains unchanged, and its north pole always points to Polaris as shown in Fig.1 (Copernicus, 2006).

Figure 1. Heliocentric model: the earth revolves continuously around its axis SN once a day, and around the sun once a year keeping its north pole always towards the Polaris

2. Two astronomical phenomena that cannot be explained by the heliocentric theory

2.1 The directions of the Big Dipper are different in different seasons

Although the sunrise, sunset and four seasons can be explained by the heliocentric model, it cannot be explained with this model that the constellations, such as the Big Dipper, observed on the earth change their directions with the change of the seasons (Chen 2021; Chen 2021). Because the constellations are composed of fixed stars and the fixed stars are relatively static, the rotation of the fixed stars observed on the earth must be caused by the change of the observer's observation direction. For example, the directions of the Big Dipper observed on the earth are different in different seasons, as shown in Fig. 2 (Chen 2022).

Figure 2. The directions of the Big Dipper are unchanged, which look changed just because the observation direction has changed.

According to the heliocentric model, when the earth revolves around the sun, the direction of its axis remains unchanged, and its north pole always points to the Polaris (Copernicus, 2006), as shown in Fig. 1. Obviously, the heliocentric model cannot explain the rotation of the Big Dipper observed on the earth because the direction of observation is unchanged and always towards the north pole of the earth.

2.2 Some stars could be observed on the earth all year round

Some fixed stars, such as the Big Dipper, can be observed on the earth all year round. This leads to the second problem. If the earth revolves around the sun, why can the Big Dipper be observed all year round? Because the sun's light is too strong, only the stars which are away from the sun can be observed at night. In other words, only the stars within the solid angle θ can be observed from the earth at night, as shown in Fig. 3. The distance between the earth and the sun is $D=149,597,870\text{km}$, and the radius of the earth is $R_E=6,371\text{km}$. So, the solid angle θ of the sky observed on the earth can be calculated as follows,

$$\text{tg}\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) = \frac{R_E}{D} = \frac{6371\text{km}}{149,597,870\text{km}} = 0.00004259 \quad (1)$$

$$\theta = 2\text{arctg}\frac{R_E}{D} = 2 \times 0.0025^\circ = 0.005^\circ \quad (2)$$

Figure 3. The stars can be observed only within the solid angle θ on the earth at night

According to the heliocentric model, in spring and autumn, as well as summer and winter, the direction of observing the stars on the earth is diametrically opposite, as shown in Fig. 4. Therefore, it is impossible to observe the same stars in spring and autumn. The same is true in summer and winter. Even in two adjacent seasons, such as mid spring and midsummer, it is impossible to observe the same stars, because the solid angle of the sky observed on the earth is only 0.005 degrees.

Therefore, the phenomenon that some stars can be observed on the earth all year round cannot be explained by the heliocentric model.

Figure 4. Earth position around the Sun in mid-spring, midsummer, mid-autumn, and mid-winter.

3 Revision of heliocentric model

The changes in its direction of the Big Dipper observed in different seasons are caused by the change of the direction of observation, which means that the direction of the earth's axis SN is changing. Only when the earth is fixed on the side of the sun can the stars within the same solid angle θ be observed throughout the year. In order to make the earth meet these

two conditions, we need to improve the heliocentric model.

The rotation of the earth around the sun can be regarded as the rotation of the sun around its axis SS, as shown in Fig. 5(a). The earth located at point A, at time t_0 , moves to point B after time Δt , with an angular velocity ω , which is equivalent to that the earth remains stationary, and point C on the sun moves to point D with an angular velocity of negative ω and the same time Δt . From this point of view, the earth is “fixed” at point A. While the earth rotates, its axis SN rotates around the axis EE, as shown in Fig 5(b).

Figure 5. Take the earth as the coordinate origin O_e . (a) the revolution of the earth around the sun is equivalent to that the sun moves with the same angular velocity in the opposite direction, and (b) while the earth rotates, its axis rotates around the axis EE.

This processing method is equivalent to coordinate transformation. It just changes the reference object of the earth's revolution around the sun, as if the center of the earth is “fixed” at point O_e , and did not affect the rotation of the earth. So, sunrise and sunset are still caused by the earth's rotation around its axis SN. However, the axis SN is no longer fixed to pointing to the Polaris, but rotates around the axis EE, resulting in changes in the four seasons, as shown in Fig. 5(b). The angle between axes SN and EE is the same as that calculated by Newton's theory, as show in Fig. 1. From this point of view, it shows that a rotating object will produce a force that repels other objects around it.

If we observe the sky on the Tropic of Cancer, our position on the earth at midnight in mid-spring, midsummer, mid-autumn, and mid-winter are shown in Fig. 6(a), Fig. 6(b), Fig. 6(c), and Fig. 6(d), respectively. The Tropic of Cancer is in the same solid angle θ where the sky can be observed at midnight in the four seasons, rotating along ellipse A_1 , A_2 , A_3 , and A_4 , as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 6. The position of the Tropic of cancer on the earth at midnight in mid-spring (a), mid-summer(b), mid-autumn (c), and mid-winter (d).

Although the position of the earth's Tropic of Cancer at midnight varies with the seasons, they are always within the same solid angle θ . So there are always some stars, such as the Big Dipper, that can be observed all year round. And because the north-pole of the earth is rotating, the stars we see are as if rotating as well. Therefore, the Big Dipper can be seen all the year, and the direction and the orientation of the Big Dipper are different in different seasons.

Figure 7. The position of the Tropic of cancer at midnight rotates along ellipse A_1 , A_2 , A_3 , and A_4 , in the four seasons.

4. Conclusion

In order to explain the two astronomical phenomena, the direction of the Big Dipper rotates with the seasons and some stars can be seen all year round, the heliocentric model is improved. Both the sun and the earth are all stationary. Except the moon, which revolves around the earth, all the other planets revolve around the sun. The earth is fixed on the side of the sun. The sky that can be observed on the earth is only within a solid angle of 0.005 degrees away from the sun. The range of the sky that can be observed on the earth is only a very small area compared with the vast universe. The rotation of the earth around its axis produces sunrise and sunset. At the same time, the earth's axis rotates around the axis perpendicular to the ecliptic plane to produce the four seasons of spring, summer, autumn and winter. Therefore, some stars, including the Big Dipper, can be observed in all seasons on the earth, but their directions and orientations are different.

Data Availability

The data underlying this article will be shared on reasonable request to the corresponding author.

References

- Copernicus N., 2006, Translated by Shihui Ye, *De Revolutionibus Orbium Coelestium*, Peking University Press.
- Chen N. F., 2021, figshare: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17169314.v2>
- Chen N.F., 2021, figshare: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.17258147.v1>
- Chen N. F., 2022, zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6476660>
- Newton I., 2008, *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica* (1822), ISBN 9780548952610, Kessinger Publishing, LLC.